

Seedling News

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Distributed to the nursery and agricultural industry of Southern Africa

SEPTEMBER 1991

Primulas: a new force in gardens

Peter Kruger

A wide range of primula Polyanthus and Acaulis flowers is available to suit all tastes.

Primulas are increasing in popularity among the bedding plant producers and keen gardeners of South Africa. The beautiful and varied colours now available, combined with the wide range of sizes, will easily make Primulas a good choice for winter and spring bedding and pot plants. Best results are obtained under cooler conditions. This plant therefore has the potential to create gardening awareness and excitement through the winter months.

A wide range of Primulas can be grown, but the most popular are the Acaulis type, commonly called Primroses. These make delightful

potted plants, in the standard size (*Pageant* series), semi-miniatures (*Lovely* series) and miniatures (*Julian* series). Their large flowers produced in distinctive rosettes on very neat plants are available in separate colours. Even under rather low light conditions, the plants remain compact and early-flowering.

Malacoides and Veris (Polyanthus) types are more popular for garden use where they live up cold, damp areas. The fragrant flowers are borne profusely in early Spring. Obconica types make excellent indoor pot plants, flowering over an extended period. ▼

Primula Pacific Giant is already well-known and is available in an extensive range of colours and shades.

Pageant primula hybrids displaying their rich colours and rounded petals. This series is particularly vigorous with excellent uniformity.

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Growing Primulas

Peter Kruger

The key factor in growing Primulas is getting the temperature right for germination. To achieve sales of flowering plants in late winter and early Spring, seed will have to be sown in our warmer months. Optimum germination temperatures are 15–18°C, although local growers are obtaining good results at up to 25°C.

Sow onto a good seedling medium and do not cover the seed as light is required to stimulate germination, although very low light levels are adequate. The seed must not be allowed to dry out during the germination process, therefore maintaining a high humidity without inducing water-logging is essential for germination success.

Seedlings must be raised at relatively low temperatures (20–25°C). Shading the greenhouse will aid in temperature control. Transplant after about nine weeks directly into 13 cm pots. Use a well-drained, light potting soil high in organic matter. Reduce watering after establishment as plants are very sensitive to wet conditions. Do not feed too much and ensure adequate

watering to prevent high salt levels. Leaf chlorosis develops easily, caused by iron deficiency. Maintain good ventilation to prevent Botrytis infection.

Primulas are a relatively long-term crop to produce, but are usually sold in individual containers, so returns on the

crop are generally high compared to bedding plants sold in punnets. Primulas are major sellers during the cool months in Europe and Japan. They are therefore ideally suited to help South African gardeners out of their winter depression. ▼

Snippets

Lettuce seed germinates best at relatively low temperatures. Growing medium temperatures of 18–20°C are generally best. However, most lettuce is consumed in summer, forcing growers to germinate seed at higher temperatures. High temperatures can cause lettuce seed to enter a secondary dormancy period known as thermodormancy. The result is poor and erratic germination, looking exactly the same as that caused by a low-vigour seed lot. Sowing seed in the afternoon, so that the critical eight hour period occurs during the night time coolness, should overcome this problem. ▼

Professional training for the nursery industry is being addressed by various training authorities. However, for those already on the job but still wanting a formal qualification, full-time study is not feasible. The Home Study College has recently introduced a School of Horticulture, after concluding an agreement with the Australian Horticultural Correspondence School. Diplomas in Horticulture, Nursery Management and other related topics are now possible through HSC.

Contact Chris Gardner at P.O.Box 4904, CAPE TOWN, 8000 for further details. ▼

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Editor's View

The comprehensive Nursery Directory advertised elsewhere in *Seedling News* represents a considerable step forward in unifying the nursery industry of South Africa. The initial value of this Directory will depend on a strong response from commercial propagation nurseries. Nurserymen should therefore ensure that they fill in and return the questionnaire promptly.

The Nursery Directory will prove extremely useful to the entire nursery industry. The substantial index will classify nurseries according to geographical region and category of plants produced.

The Seedling Growers' Association of Southern Africa elected a new National Committee at the AGM, following a very successful Symposium. Association members voted to allow two allied trade (supplier member) committee members. This should prove greatly beneficial to the Association by introducing a new perspective. Queries regarding the Association should be directed to the Director of Operations, Box 11636, DORPSPRUIT, 3206.

The categories used in the index are based on their usefulness to purchasers of plants, without becoming too bogged down in minor detail. It should therefore prove an excellent quick reference to guide wholesale plant buyers to make profitable nursery contact.

The loosening-up of international trading ties for South African businesses might prove a particularly strong incentive to use our climate (and in particular our southern hemisphere time difference) to produce plant material for export. This directory will be the obvious choice of

reference for export agents wanting to make contact with the nursery industry in this country. ▼

SEEDLING NEWS

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Fungus gnats

Warrick Nelson

A problem becoming more apparent in nurseries (including tunnels) is the appearance of fungus gnats. The damage they cause is not easily seen and is often attributed to other causes. The adults are mosquito-like flies. Their presence is usually the first obvious indication of infestation. They are 2-4 mm in size, black, and tend to hover in and above the leaf canopy. The adults do not appear to cause any plant damage.

Fungus gnat larvae are legless, semi-transparent worms up to 5 mm long. They typically occur in the top layers of the growing medium, but are quite difficult to see. They may cause direct damage by eating the fine root hairs or stripping the outer layer off larger roots. This type of damage is not very common, nor usually severe. They have occasionally been found to tunnel into soft, succulent stem tissue.

Fungus gnats are typically secondary pests of plants. They normally only attack damaged or otherwise weakened plants. However, they are known to transmit verticillium wilt and are also suspected of transmitting pythium and other fungal diseases. It is for this

reason that they should be controlled as soon as adult flies are noticed.

Control of fungus gnats should include elimination of favoured breeding sites. Moist surfaces covered in algae or decaying organic matter should be eliminated. Drainage must be installed in and around the nursery, with perhaps a layer of stone chips or ash beneath tables to reduce algae growth. Apart from aiding fungus gnat control, eliminating algae in the nursery should improve safety, particularly on walkways. Remove weeds and dead plant matter from beneath tables and in drains.

Chemical control of existing adults and larvae is possible. Products mentioned in various reports for fungus gnat control include diazinon, diflubenzuron, mercaptothion and oxamyl. None appear to be registered for use in nurseries and advice from a chemical supplier should be obtained before treating plants. Larvae control is usually achieved by light drenching of the medium. An aerosol form of insecticide should be used for adult fly control. ▼

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Vegetables such as cabbage, broccoli, brussels sprouts, kohlrabi and cauliflower may help reduce the risk of gastrointestinal and respiratory tract cancer.

Fruits and vegetables (and whole grain cereals such as oatmeal, bran and wheat) may help lower the risk of colorectal cancer.

In short, make sure you do what your mother always told you to do. Eat your vegetables.

In short, make sure you do what your mother always told you to do. Eat your vegetables.

Feeding the nation

Vegetables can and should contribute significantly to the vitamin and mineral nutrients in our diets.

Two American trends are likely to provide a spin-off for South African vegetable growers. The California Department of Health Services is promoting a five-a-day plan for fruit and vegetables, while the FDA (Food and Drug Administration) is considering labeling of nutrient value on vegetable produce (much the same as ingredient labelling on manufactured foods).

Retailers can expect to increase their sales of vegetables significantly through the implementation of these measures. Consumers are generally very interested in the products they buy. Adding information on the nutritional value and ideas on how to use the products should help increase the volume of vegetables eaten. ▼

Vitamin round-up

- A Synthesised in the body from carotene obtained in green and yellow vegetables.
- B* A complex of vitamins obtained from most fresh vegetables, particularly legumes, beetroot and cabbage families.
- C* Fresh leafy and fruit vegetables, particularly if eaten raw.
- D Dietary requirement easily supplied by synthesis in the skin on exposure to sunlight.
- K An important blood-clotting agent obtained from green, leafy vegetables.

* These usually dissolve into the cooking water and are therefore often thrown out with the water.

VAT's up?

John Rycroft

Financial Director, Starke Ayres

As current V.A.T. registration stands, businesses that have a turnover in excess of R150 000 must register for V.A.T. Those that sell less than R150 000 have an option to register or not. This option needs to be considered carefully.

The decision to register or not will, to a large extent, depend on the registration status of the customers. Not registering will simplify book-keeping as there is no input and output V.A.T. to calculate, no payment to the Receiver of Revenue, no return to fill in every two months, and no necessity for administrative records identifying the V.A.T. component of sales. However, V.A.T. paid on goods cannot be claimed from the Receiver, and will therefore constitute part of their cost.

Where registered customers purchase from an unregistered business, the V.A.T. component of their purchase cannot be claimed back. This might mean that these customers would prefer to do business with a registered supplier as their costs could

be 10% higher from the unregistered supplier. Businesses which deal mainly in zero-rated items or export sales would lose their V.A.T. advantage if they are not registered vendors.

So, if the small business is to supply larger customers, zero-rated items, or export customers, registration is probably advisable. Certainly any business aiming to disclose a turnover approaching R150 000 in the near future needs to consider V.A.T. in its accounting. The small business which does not fit this situation would probably be better off not registering, as the only V.A.T. to take into account would be that paid on its own inputs.

V.A.T. is here, and here to stay. Despite the current hullabaloo, we will accommodate and learn to live with this tax, as we have done with the others. The concept is in essence simple, and nothing that a little book-keeping cannot overcome.

I am happy to answer any further queries regarding V.A.T. and can be contacted at (021)543231.

Seedling Tray Supply

The announcement this week that seedling nurserymen can look forward to an improved supply of seedling trays in future has been welcomed in nursery circles.

"For too long, the Seedling Industry has had to put up with an inconsistent quality and erratic supply of seedling trays" says Mr Warrick Nelson, National Product Manager (Seedling Propagation Systems) for Starke Ayres, exclusive suppliers of the "Speedling" and "Long Life" range of Multistyrene seedling trays.

"This seriously hampers production planning and makes it difficult for nurserymen, who run tight production schedules, to meet their delivery deadlines" he says.

According to Mr Nelson, recent developments in the industry are expected to improve the situation dramatically:

"The decision taken by Starke Ayres (Pty) Limited a year ago to stock up its warehouses with seedling trays during the off-season, despite the cost implications, has greatly reduced the pressure on our manufacturer and enabled him to streamline his production. As a result, we are now able to offer a much improved service to our customers."

"Automa must be congratulated for standing firm on their decision taken some time ago to continue manufacturing seedling trays without compromising quality, in spite of very strong competition on price in the market place. Recent developments have proved, without a doubt, that the decision was the right one", he said.

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STARKE AYRES NURSERY DIRECTORY

What is *SAND* ?

SAND is a comprehensive list of South African nurseries.

It is therefore a useful working document for plant purchasers.

Features of *SAND*

Important features of *SAND* include full details of the nursery, with fax numbers and contact personnel. For Quick reference, a substantial index is supplied.

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DATE

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159 Edenplant Laboratories P.O.Box 333, EDENGLLEN, 2376. S. Smurf Tel: 011-
Fax: 011-765432. Tissue Culture : Ferns, Indoor, Crops

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DATE OF PUBLICATION: DECEMBER 1991

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TUNNEL TALK

Nunhems visit

Starke Ayres was pleased to welcome and arrange Farmers' Days for two visitors from Nunhems Zaden. Jeroen de Haas (with tie, on left) and John Willems (with tie, on right) paid an extended visit to see at first hand the growing conditions faced by tunnel growers. They were able to determine the best cultivar choices for various regions and climates, while also gathering data to inform Nunhems' breeders.

Tunnel growers around the country were able to benefit from the sound technical and marketing advice of these two top managers. Nunhems are the breeders and suppliers of many excellent tunnel varieties of cucumbers (*Bella* is the most popular) and tomatoes (such as *Meran*) used in South Africa. New tunnel crops proving profitable in Holland could be introduced to South Africa, where tunnel production is almost solely concentrated on cucumbers.

Some of the points noted should be of particular concern to South African cucumber growers. Light is often disregarded as a limiting factor because of our normally high light levels. However, light can limit fruit production in a number of circumstances. During winter, and in tunnels with older (and dirtier) plastic, plant population should

be reduced. A large leaf standing upright above the top trellis wire has a big shading effect on plants. This umbrella leaf must be pruned off.

Ventilation and temperature are commonly not under sufficient control to achieve top yields. Low temperatures can result in more than one flower per node and short, spiky fruit. High temperatures tend to place the plant under stress, particularly when

combined with high humidity. The reduced transpiration resulting from this combination results in bad fruit colouration, poor fruit shelf-life and an increase in fungal disease problems. Ventilation is important and is aided by choosing a cultivar with an open habit, such as *Bella*, pruning old leaves up to 70 cm on the main stem, and encouraging an adequate draft of air through the tunnels. ▼

Fertigation simplified

Warrick Nelson

Applying fertilizers with irrigation water is a common technique in seedling nurseries and tunnels. Two methods are used for mixing the fertilizer with the irrigation water, and each has its advantages.

Venous types of fertilizer injectors are available at different prices and for different sized operations. However, a common problem typically not addressed when considering these injectors is the chemical incompatibility of hydroponic nutrients at high concentrations. For example, calcium tends to react with sulphate to form gypsum, which is insoluble. As a result, many hydroponic growers are battling to supply balanced nutrients to their plants, with consequent growth and quality defects.

Bulk tank mixing sounds far less glamorous. However, it has certain

distinct advantages over the concentrate mix and injector system. Firstly, the chances of making a mistake are much reduced. Any error is likely to have a minimal growth effect as the degree of error will be small. A small adjustment on an injector can have far-reaching growth effects, particularly if it is not discovered quickly. A lot of extra fertilizer would have to be routinely added to the bulk tank mix to cause similar growth problems. Whichever system is used, a weekly or daily check on fertilizer used is recommended.

Secondly, a reserve of water on site is a risk-reducing feature. This should be sufficient for at least one day, preferably more, considering the implications of a lengthy pump breakdown.

Thirdly, monitoring of nutrient strengths by means of a conductivity meter is not necessary once the correct

amount of nutrient has been calculated. This monitoring should probably still be done to monitor leachate salt content, but the necessity becomes far less critical to successful management.

A bulk tank mix can be set up in a number of ways. The easiest to manage is to use two ten thousand litre reservoirs. Sufficient nutrient (twenty kilogrammes of Chemicult for most requirements) is added to the tank during filling. The tank should be at least half full. A pump is then used to circulate the water to dissolve the nutrient. Once the tank is full, the same pump is then used to pump the nutrient solution to the plants. While this tank is being used, the other tank is filled and nutrients added in the same way. The fertilizer should not first be mixed in a

Continued on page 9

TUNNEL TALK

Tunnel nutrition Home blend or pre-mixed?

Ken Jeanes

Tunnel crops require sophisticated blends of nutrients. All necessary elements need to be supplied in precise amounts to the plants on a daily basis. These nutrients must be in a readily available form and in the correct ratios. Any imbalance will decrease the yield potential.

Much research has been carried out on the nutrition of tunnel crops. The result is the development of various nutrient solutions. Though there is some variation between the solutions, all supply each of the elements within a limited range.

Many tunnel growers do not realise the complexity of nutrition and so opt for home blends of fertilizer which appear to work out a lot cheaper. Experience in the field indicates that in most cases this does not pay off as nutrient imbalances are frequently seen and unhealthy plants common. Such plants are more vulnerable to diseases and are unable to produce good yields. Common problems observed are poor N:K ratios, often favouring vegetative growth, and deficiencies of Ca, S and Fe. Growers are also tempted to mix their blend as a concentrate and then dilute it in a tank later. This can result in the precipitation of certain complexes, such as calcium sulphate, which is then unavailable to the plants.

Fertilization simplified

continued

small amount of water. The dry fertilizer must be put into the bulk tank, otherwise the reaction of calcium and sulphate will occur in the same way as in the injector system.

Each tank should be emptied fully before refilling and adding more nutrients to avoid an excess of nutrients building up in the tank. Every few months, sediment which may have formed on the base of the tank can easily be syphoned out.

The size of the tanks will depend on the size of the nursery. The operation could work just as easily with more than two tanks, particularly if a reserve of water has to be built up overnight.

Bulk tank mixes are operationally sound, easy to manage and provide a surprisingly economical means of mixing nutrients with water. Their low technology requirement can be a distinct advantage.

There are many other draw-backs to the use of home blends, such as

Element	Range ppm	Chemicult
N	150-180	150-160
P	40-50	46
K	230-280	247
Ca	140-160	150
S	95-120	101
Mg	35-45	39
Zn	0,1-0,2	0,1
Fe	3-6	3,3
Mn	0,5	0,5
Cu	0,05	0,05
Mo	0,02	0,02
B	0,1-0,5	0,5

The range of elements found in most recommendations for nutrient solutions for tunnel production. Chemicult has been specifically formulated for South African conditions.

unskilled labour and small mistakes resulting in large expenses. Unhealthy, deficient plants with deformed fruit are also indicative of the difficulty involved in trying to obtain a balanced blend from the common soluble fertilisers available.

An example of a complete hydroponic feed with all necessary elements in the correct concentrations and proportions is Chemicult. This product was developed by experts in tunnel nutrition, specifically for tunnel production. Chemicult may be used at up to fifty times concentration as it is available in two separate portions, thus preventing the formation of calcium sulphate.

The question of tunnel nutrition is not so much a case of cheap or expensive, but rather balancing risk and investment capital.

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Get the *SAND* In your eyes

Seedling Quality for Foresters

D.G.M. Donald

Professor of Forestry, University of Stellenbosch

During my recent sabbatical in the USA, I was introduced to a new seedling ratio that appeared to measure quality of seedlings in a more meaningful way than I have so far tested. It is the ratio between the dry weight of the foliage and the collar diameter.

I tested this parameter on data from a *Pinus elliottii* nursery comparison study, replacing foliage dry weight with total shoot dry weight. The previous conclusion from this trial had been that the nursery system and seedling size did not affect the growth of the trees (measured at 33 months from transplanting).¹ However, using this new parameter, it is clear that increasing seedling size had a marked effect on volume of timber produced (see graph). Even more interesting was the difference between the Speedling system (model 128 tray) and all other systems on trial.

The thin collar diameter and low shoot mass of the Speedling tray plants should have produced a very low biomass. Instead, it was up with the leading producers and out-performing most other systems. This effect is probably due to the lack of transplanting shock as it was the only system on trial in which the root system was not severely disturbed at planting.

Collar diameter has been strongly correlated with seedling density in bare-root systems. Reducing the density of seedlings has been shown to have a marked increase in timber yields. This confirms the importance of this seedling quality parameter. If the hypothesis that the small Speedling tray seedlings out-performed seedlings from other systems because of a lack of planting shock is correct, how would stronger plants perform with the same advantage? The cost of producing the plants is greater, but if the hypothesis is correct, the additional yield should give an excellent return.

Companies wishing to investigate this parameter or who have existing data which may be useful in determining the accuracy of the hypothesis should contact me at the university. ▼

Model	Plants per m ²
72	310
98	421
128	550
200	860

Decreasing the density of seedlings in the nursery has been demonstrated to improve timber yield after planting of bare-root seedlings. Reducing the density of seedlings is the only way of increasing collar diameter and therefore increasing the quality parameter.

Bare-root seedlings show a clear correlation between seedling size at time of transplanting and amount of timber produced. The Speedling system is clearly on a different regression line. Current evidence strongly suggests that a similar regression exists for seedlings transplanted with minimal root disturbance and shock.

Nursery Survey

System	Pinus	Eucalyptus	Acacia	Total	Percent
Speedling 128	54	81	9	143	60
Speedling 128 deep	15	17	—	32	13
Speedling 98	5	1	—	7	3
Unigro	8	24	—	32	13
SAPPI 49	3	1	—	4	2
Polypot/sleeve	9	2	—	11	5
Box	3	—	—	3	1
Bare-root	9	—	—	9	4
Totals	106	126	9	241	
Percentage	44	52	4		

Summary of commercial forest plants produced in 1990 by genera and systems in millions of plants.

Professor Donald (University of Stellenbosch) has recently conducted a survey of forest transplant production in South Africa. The biggest change compared to his previous survey¹ was the threefold increase in number of seedlings produced, but with a 25 percent reduction in number of nurseries. Clearly the size of nurseries

has increased. Another factor he noted was the increased importance of nurseries owned by the major forestry companies. The table summarises the production of forestry transplants by genera and nursery system. ▼

¹ Donald, D.G.M. 1986. South African Nursery Practice—The State of the Art. South African Forestry Journal 139:36-47.

Cornucopia F₁ hybrid sweetcorn displays attributes particularly desirable for both the grower and the consumer. This high-yielding variety produces large cobs with lovely golden-coloured kernels on a sturdy plant displaying excellent resistance to Rust.

Starflower F₁ hybrid squash produces excellent quality, highly attractive fruits. The yield potential of this cultivar is outstanding, particularly considering the uniformity in size and shape of the fruits.

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Eelworm a problem?

Warrick Nelson

Eelworms (nematodes) are a serious pest in South African soils. They are often present in large numbers and can totally ruin a harvest.

Recent results from trials in the Tala Valley (near Pietermaritzburg) have shown that some of the soils are so contaminated with eelworm that a lettuce crop is impossible without costly chemical control measures.

Eelworms are microscopic worm-like organisms which feed off plant roots. The root-knot species causes unsightly swellings on affected roots. Numerous

other species exist, many of which cause little obvious visible damage. A few species do not affect plants, while some even attack other eelworms.

Eelworm damage to plants is not limited only to reducing the yield potential of the plant. Crops such as carrots can be damaged sufficiently seriously to reduce their market value without necessarily reducing yield tonnage.

Chemical controls have been developed to eliminate eelworm from cropped soils. Although these

chemicals are generally very effective, they are not used as a general control because of their cost. The desire to cut down on chemical usage on vegetable farms is also being pushed by consumer demands and environmental concerns.

Fortunately, a number of safe methods of controlling eelworm numbers are available. Physical exclusion by not irrigating with very muddy water is possible. If the river water is very muddy, chances are that eelworm have been carried down in the water from higher upstream.

Filters are available to filter out eelworm, but this option is hardly practical on an extensive basis.

Other means of control employ natural eelworm toxins produced by crops. Marigolds are commonly quoted for this purpose. Other plants suitable for this purpose are ryegrass (as a short rotation crop) and green manures of sudangrass and rapeseed. Trials using green manures have indicated that eelworm control can be as good as with chemicals. Green manures are typically sown just after mid-summer and ploughed in during autumn or spring.

Seaweeds are known to help reduce eelworm damage in crop plants. Some of the effects reported are nothing short of spectacular. This highly economical means of reducing eelworm damage is particularly exciting since many farmers already use Kelpak (a locally manufactured plant growth stimulant made from seaweed) on their crops.

Eelworms should be considered whenever a crop performs poorly. They are extremely widespread and chances are that they are the cause of the problem. ▼

Tomato roots grown in eelworm-infested soil. Note how a foliar application of Kelpak markedly reduces the damage caused by the eelworm. A = control, B = treated plants.

NEW

SEED MATE LL

Starke Ayres proudly announce the new improved SEED MATE Long Life seedling tray. The lower density centre ensures healthy seedlings which benefit from the excellent insulating properties of polystyrene. The higher density top skin puts toughness where it is needed most. Strength and durability — plus all these benefits:

- Continuous curved cell walls for quick release
- No holes or grooves to harbour disease
- Larger cell volume for more roots
- Available in 98, 128 and 200 cell configurations
- Ozone-friendly
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- Easier cleaning
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